

ISic1214

I.Sicily inscription 1214

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Observed in the Bishop's palace in Lipari; circumstances of discovery unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, lost

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Γ(αῖου) Πουβλειλί
2. ου Γόργου
3. Κλωδίας
4. Ἰλάρας

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 492818

EDCS 39101578

PHI 140698

PHI 334841

Bibliography

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